

Tsallis Entropy is No Longer Linked Maximum Probability if $q \neq 1$? Part 3

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. March 12, 2025

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be obtained by maximizing a math function called entropy subject to two a priori constraints: $\sum_i p_i = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p_i = E_{\text{total}}$. Mathematically, the extremization process links the constraint variable e_i to the probability via a math function called entropy. Maximizing entropy, if entropy is simply given as a math function, does not seem to have any link to maximization of probability or minimization of information. In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, however, the entropy is Shannon's entropy: $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ which follow from taking \ln of Probability of N trials = Product over i $p(e_i)$ power $(Np(e_i))$. Thus, Shannon's entropy is linked with probability and so maximizing subject to two a priori constraints does minimize information as much as possible. This, however, does not change the fact that the extremization process links a math function in $p(e_i)$ to a constraint.

The reason we stress this point is because one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution through reaction time-reversal balance together with conservation of energy, i.e. $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4)$. Taking \ln of the latter and equation with the former yields: $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. No consideration of maximizing probability or minimizing information appears here. The key is to link probability with e_i . Specifically: $\ln(\exp(-e_i/T)) = -e_i/T$ and $p(e_i) \frac{d}{dp(e_i)} \ln(p(e_i)) = \text{constant}$.

We argue that given the two approaches of obtaining the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, one could suggest two different fundamental statistical postulates. The first is that one must maximize probability (minimize) information subject to a priori constraints. This is the usual interpretation that is taken and is then assumed to apply to all statistical situations. The second approach is to try to argue that there exists a function $F(p(e_i))$ such that $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ B1 (the information) and $\frac{d}{dp(e_i)} F(p(e_i)) = \text{constant}$ B2. This postulate has nothing to do with maximization of probability.

It turns out that for the Maxwell-Boltzmann scenario, these two are equivalent, but that does not mean that they need to be equivalent in other scenarios.

One such scenario is the Tsallis entropy case in which one begins with an a priori constraint: $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q$. The Tsallis approach assumes that the fundamental postulates of statistical mechanics are B1 and B2 regardless of whether probability is maximized or not. We have argued in Parts 1 and 2 that it is not linked with the maximization of probability except in the $q=1$ case, but if B1 and B2 are the fundamental postulates, then that is not a problem.

Maximization of Probability/ Minimization of Information

Boltzmann's entropy is $-k \ln(\text{number of states})$. If one wishes to maximize probability, i.e. minimize information, then one wishes to as many states possible consistent with a priori constraints. This seems like a reasonable assumption, i.e. one tries to solve a physical problem using as little information as possible. The catch, however, is that there may be relevant information of which one is unaware, but nature is not. Thus, the maximization of probability/minimization of information is an assumption, it seems.

Shannon's entropy is consistent with that of Boltzmann and follows from writing the probability of N trials:

$$\text{Probability}(N \text{ trials}) = \text{Product over } i \text{ } p(e_i) \text{ power } (Np(e_i)) \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{Taking In of both sides yields: } \sum \text{ over } i \text{ } p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((2))$$

((2)) is minus Shannon's entropy.

One must then maximize ((2)) subject to a priori constraints such as: $\sum \text{ over } i \text{ } p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum \text{ over } i \text{ } e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{total}}$ in order to find the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

One may note, however, that ultimately the maximization process links $p(e_i)$ to $-e_i/T$, which may be called the information present. Thus, even though one begins with the notion of Probability (N trials) the actual result is link $p(e_i)$ with $-e_i/T$. If this is the goal, one may introduce an inverse function to $p(e_i)$ i.e.

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((3))$$

Of course, there must be a way in which to calculate ((3)). The maximization of probability/minimization of information seems to be the accepted way.

Time Reversal Elastic Scattering Balance

It is possible to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution without any maximization process. In such a case:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((4a)) \text{ and } p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4) \quad ((4b))$$

$$\text{Taking In of } ((4b)) \text{ and linking with } ((4a)) \text{ yields: } p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((5))$$

A person finding ((5)) using this approach would have no sense of probability of N trials being maximized or information minimized. In fact, one could suggest that $F(p(e_i))$ form ((3)) is found through:

$$p(e_i) \frac{d}{dp(e_i)} F(p(e_i)) \text{ suggesting that } F(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i)) \text{ in this case } \quad ((6))$$

There is no particular reason why a person solving for the MB distribution using time reversal balance could suggest ((6)) as a fundamental statistical principle and ignore maximization of probability altogether. We suggest that this is what happens in the Tsallis entropy case.

Tsallis Entropy

The Tsallis entropy case considers an a priori constraint:

$$\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q \quad (7)$$

There is no reason that such a constraint cannot appear in nature even though the normalized probability is $p(e_i)$, i.e. $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$. The question then becomes: How does one find $p(e_i)$? We have argued in Parts 1 and 2, that maximizing a probability using the unnormalized $p(e_i)^q$ does not yield Tsallis entropy. On the other hand, one may use ((6)) with the first factor $p(e_i)$ replaced with $p(e_i)^q$. Then:

$$p(e_i)^q \frac{d}{dp(i)} F(p(e_i)) \rightarrow F(p(e_i)) = C + p(e_i)^{1-q} \quad (8)$$

Given that one must obtain Shannon's result, $F(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i))$ or $q=1$, one has:

$$F(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i)) = \frac{\sum_i p(e_i)^q - 1}{1-q} \quad (9)$$

Thus, probability is maximized only in the $q=1$ case, but the general idea of ((6)) applies for all q . In other words, the Tsallis approach assumes that maximization of probability/minimization of information is only a key idea for $q=1$. It suggests that linking $p(e_i)$ to $-e_i/T$ is the real key and suggests that ((6)) is the way to do so. There is an information function of $p(e_i)$ which retrieves $-e_i/T$ and $d/dp(e_i)$ of this information function multiplied by the probability used in the a priori constraint yields a constant. This is a very different viewpoint from an a priori maximization of probability, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Parts 1 and 2 we noted that Tsallis entropy does not maximize probability/minimize information except for $q=1$. The Tsallis approach seems to indicate that the universally held notion that statistical mechanics means minimizing information except that held in a priori constraints is not the key idea. It only happens to hold for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case. This MB case, however, may be solved without any notion to maximum probability or maximizing entropy subject to a priori constraints simply using conservation of energy in two body collisions, $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$, and $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4)$. If one uses this approach, one might suggest that the fundamental statistical idea is: $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and $p(e_i) \frac{d}{dp(i)} \ln(p(e_i)) = \text{constant}$. In such a case, one might argue that it is only a coincidence that overall probability is maximized (which is akin to using Shannon's entropy).

If one adopts this viewpoint, one may generalize to the case in which the constraint is: $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q$, which appears physically in nature. One may suggest a function $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and $p(e_i)^q \frac{d}{dp(e_i)} F(p(e_i)) = \text{constant}$. This leads to the Tsallis \ln_q which only becomes \ln in the $q=1$ case. In other words, only in the $q=1$ case does one have maximum probability.